

LITERACY AND NUMERACY SKILLS ON WORD PROBLEM IN MATHEMATICS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

CLARISSA N. MIRANDA

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8522-721X>

cninoblamiranda@gmail.com

Batangas State University

JPLPC Malvar G. Leviste St., Poblacion, Malvar, Batangas, Philippines

ABSTRACT

In Mathematics, problem solving is the basis of learning. The students must be skilful in solving a word problem. However, only some of the students can solve problems and others are experiencing difficulties. Hence, this qualitative-descriptive study is conducted to examine students' errors and learning attitudes when solving Mathematical word problems. The sample consists of thirty-three (33) Grade 11 students of FAITH Fidelis Senior High, Tanauan City, Batangas. Making use of Newman's Error Analysis consisting of decoding, comprehension, transformation, process skill, and encoding stages, the researcher was able to determine the stages where students usually commit errors. It is also the objective of the researcher to examine the students' learning attitude in solving word problems as to three components, namely, affective, behavioural, and cognitive. It also determined the different strategies used by teachers in correcting the errors of students in solving word problems. The results showed that students only have a developing level of proficiency in the transformation (78.79%), process (79.80%), and encoding (80.81%) stages of solving word problems. In the decoding stage, students are on the advanced level of proficiency (13.13%) and on the proficient level (23.23%) on the comprehension stage of solving word problems. This study also revealed that students possess a positive attitude in the affective and cognitive component but acquire a negative attitude in the behavioural component of learning in solving word problems. Lastly, the study proposed a Mathematical learning strategy derived from the different strategies used by teacher in correcting error in solving word problems in Mathematics. These strategies can help students with the proper way of conceptualizing word problems.

Keywords: Mathematics, Literacy and Numeracy Skills, Newman's Error Analysis, Philippines